
Photostability of a photochromic naphthopyran dye in different sol-gel prepared ormosil coatings

Rosario Pardo · Marcos Zayat · David Levy

Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid, C.S.I.C., 28049 Cantoblanco, Madrid, Spain

D.Levy

e-mail: d.levy@icmm.csic.es

R. Pardo

e-mail: rpardo@icmm.csic.es

M. Zayat

e-mail: Marcos.Zayat@icmm.csic.es

Abstract A photochromic naphthopyran derivative was embedded in sol-gel prepared thin ormosil films. The resulting samples show high transparency and exhibit a strong red colouration upon irradiation with UV light. The photostability of the photochromic molecules is strongly related to the nature of the embedding ormosil matrix. The introduction of organic functional groups into the inner pore surface of the matrix allows tailoring the chemical environment where the dye molecules will be allocated, in terms of the effectiveness of the interaction between the photochromic molecules and the Si-OH groups on the surface of the pores, affecting the stability of the molecules upon prolonged exposition to UV light.

The photostability of the molecules was increased in matrices functionalized with larger organic groups, or with larger amount of modifying groups. In this way the photodegradation of the photochromic molecules could be reduced by a factor of 5, as compared with the photodegradation of the molecules in unfunctionalized silica matrix.

Keywords Photostability · Photochromic · Ormosil · Naphthopyran

Introduction

The photochromism of the benzopyrans and naphthopyrans was first reported by Becker et al. in the early 1960's [1]. The

photochromism of these molecules involves a photoinduced cleavage of the C(sp³)-O bond of the pyran ring leading to an equilibrium between the closed (colourless) and open (coloured) forms [2]. The system reverts thermally to its original closed form, as shown in Fig. 1.

Photochromic naphthopyran derivatives have been studied extensively owing to the possibility of obtaining a photochromic response in a wide range of the visible spectrum from yellow to red [3–5]. The photochromic properties of these molecules such as, the absorption spectra upon irradiation with UV light and the bleaching kinetics (rate of recovery of the original whiteness) have been studied in different solvents [4, 6] or dispersed in organic polymer matrices [7–11]. The usage of polymer matrices is a good choice for the entrapment of photochromic molecules, however it is limited by the low stability of the matrix upon UV irradiation [12, 13].

The Sol-Gel process, being a low temperature method, allows the preparation of hybrid organic-inorganic ormosil matrices and the introduction of optically active organic molecules in these solid matrices [14–17]. In a previous work, we have demonstrated the feasibility of introducing photochromic naphthopyran derivatives into sol-gel ormosil matrices [18]. The properties of the photochromic molecules dispersed in solid matrices depend strongly on the polarity of the environment in which the molecules are located [19]. Moreover, the size and shape of the pores containing the dye molecules have an important effect on the spectral and kinetic behaviour of the photochromic system, as it may provoke steric inhibitions during molecule opening-closing process [20–24]. Recently, we reported on the effect of different functional groups in the ormosil network on the photochromic properties of the embedded naphthopyran molecules [25].

The stability of the photochromic molecules is one of the important parameters to take into consideration in optical

applications. The UV radiation, needed to operate the photochromic device, is also responsible for the degradation of the photochromic molecules and the progressive loss of the effect. The first studies dealing with the photodegradation of photochromic compounds upon prolonged exposition to UV light were carried out by R. Gautron on the late 1960's [26]. The photostability of photochromic molecules of the indolinospiropyran and indolinospirooxazine families were studied in solvent solution [27–30] and in the solid state [31]. Additives were also used to improve the photostability of photochromic spirooxazines in Sol-Gel coatings [32, 33]. Salemi-Delvaux et al. [34, 35] and Balliet [36] reported on the photostability of photochromic naphthopyran derivatives in solution and polymeric networks, respectively.

The objective of the present work is to study the photostability of photochromic naphthopyran molecules embedded in ormosil matrices. In order to optimize the photostability of the molecules, different organic functional groups (R) will be used to functionalize the pore surface in the ormosil matrix. These groups will form the inner surface of the pores, where the photochromic molecules will be allocated, and hence will have an important effect on photochromic properties of the molecules and its stability upon irradiation with UV-light.

The ability to improve the photostability of the photochromic molecules in ormosil matrices will be of great interest from the point of view of the future applications.

Experimental

Materials

Tetracetoxyasilane (TAS), Phenyl triethoxysilane (PhTES), pentafluorophenyl triethoxysilane (pFPhTES), butyl triethoxysilane (BuTES) and propyl triethoxysilane (PrTES), were from ABCR. Methyl triethoxysilane (MeTES) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were purchased from Aldrich Chemicals. Ethyl triethoxysilane (EtTES) from Fluka and Ethanol (Merck). For all preparations double-distilled water was used. The photochromic dye used for the preparation of samples 3-(2,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3H-naphtho[2,1-b]pyran was generously donated by PPG Industries, Inc. The dye is colourless at dark and acquires a deep red colouration upon exposure to UV light. The chemical structure of the dye is given in Fig. 1.

Preparation of coatings

Samples were prepared from mixtures of tetracetoxyasilane (TAS) and the organically modified alkoxides (RTES) in the appropriate ratio. The R groups are the organic functional substituents in the precursor, which will form the inner pore surface of the ormosil matrix. These groups used for the preparation of the different matrices were selected from size and polarity considerations and affinity with the

Fig. 1 Chemical structure of the naphthopyran dye and different stereoisomers of the open form (merocyanines)

Table 1 Chemical composition of the sols used for film deposition. R accounts for Me, Et, Pr, Bu, pFPh and Ph

Sample name	Molar composition				
	IAS	KIES	H ₂ O	Dye	R/Si
R90	0.20	1.80	6.20	0.01	0.90
R70	0.60	1.40	6.60	0.01	0.70
R50	1.00	1.00	7.00	0.01	0.50
R30	1.40	0.60	7.40	0.01	0.30
R10	1.80	0.20	7.80	0.01	0.10
R0	2.00	0.00	8.00	0.01	0.00

photochromic dye. The amount of water to hydrolyzing group was kept 1:1 in all samples. The introduction of photochromic dyes into a sol is limited by the low stability of the dyes in the acidic medium of acid catalyzed sols. In this sense, acetoxy precursors were chosen, which release acetic acid slowly during hydrolysis, leading to a gentle catalysis of the sol [18]. The sols were allowed to hydrolyze for 24 h under stirring at 25°C. The photochromic dye was added after the hydrolysis of the sol, as a THF solution, to reach a photochromic-dye:Si molar ratio of 1:200. THF was used as solvent due to the possibility to obtain highly concentrated solutions and good miscibility with the coating sol.

The deposition of the films about glass slides was carried out after the addition of the dye using the spin-coating technique. A sample volume of 0.1 ml was used for preparation of each film with the sample holder spinning at 2000 rpm. The films were cured for 24 h at 100°C. The samples were named after the organic substituents used for preparation followed by the R/Si molar ratio in the matrix. Table 1 summarizes the composition of the sols used for film preparation.

Characterization

The photochromic samples were irradiated with a 365 nm, 100W, B-100AP UV lamp from UVP, giving a UV-light intensity on the sample of 8.9 mW/cm². The absorption spectra of the resulting films as well as the kinetics of the bleaching at dark were measured in a Varian Cary 50 Bio UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The absorption spectra were measured between 300 and 800 nm, and are given as \diamond Abs ($A_{a,i} - A_{b,i}$), where $A_{a,i}$ and $A_{b,i}$ are the absorption after and before irradiation, respectively. The decay of the photochromic effect was monitored vs. time at the wavelength of the maximum absorption of each sample (visible) at 25°C. The kinetic constants were calculated from the bleaching curves using a bi-exponential decay equation. $t_{1/2}$ is defined as the time required by the sample to reach \diamond Abs_{max}/2 during the thermal bleaching. The thickness of the films was measured with a surface roughness measuring system SurfTest SV-3000H4.

Table 2 Thickness of the samples prepared with different R groups

Samples R groups	Thickness, e μ m	Samples % Ph groups	Thickness, e μ m
Me50	0.68	Ph0	0.30
Et50	0.64	Ph10	0.60
Pr50	0.73	Ph20	0.75
Bu50	0.80	Ph30	0.90
pFPh50	0.75	Ph50	1.20
Ph50	1.2	Ph90	2.50

Results and discussion

The nature and amount of organic functional groups (R) of the ormoer determine the polarity of the inner surface of the pores, the pore volume and pore-size distribution in the films [37]. The photochromic properties and the photostability of the embedded molecules can be tailored by the composition of the ormosil matrix where the molecules will be allocated. The thickness of the samples was found to depend on the composition of the matrix used to embed the photochromic molecules. Table 2 summarizes the thickness of samples prepared with different functional groups and different amount of groups in the matrix.

Photochromic properties

The photochromic properties of the naphthopyran (NP) molecules such as, the absorption spectra upon irradiation with UV light and the kinetics of the bleaching were measured in ormosil matrices with different organic substituents.

The absorption band of the irradiated NP molecules embedded in different ormosil matrices shows a significant shift to the blue as the polarity of the matrix is reduced, as shown in Fig. 2(a). The incorporation of R groups into the structure results in a decrease of the polarity of the matrix, which is a function of the nature of the R group and its loading in the matrix [22]. This effect is due to the lower polarity of the R groups attached to its surface and the fact that large organic chains may hinder the influence of the OH groups of the pores surface, reducing furthermore the polarity of the cage as sensed by the dye molecule [25]. Figure 2(b) gives the spectral position of the absorption band of the photochromic molecules embedded in different ormosil matrices.

The coloured photochromic films undergo a thermal bleaching (at dark) upon cessation of UV irradiation, recovering their original uncoloured closed form. The bleaching kinetics, measured by monitoring the absorption of the different samples vs. time at the maximum of the absorption band, was found to depend strongly on the matrix used for the encapsulation of the photochromic molecules. Figure 3 shows the kinetics of the thermal bleaching of the photochromic dye in R-modified silica matrices. A bi-exponential decay

Fig. 2 (a) UV-Vis spectra of photochromic naphthopyran molecules embedded in different ormosil matrices upon irradiation with UV light; (b) Position of the spectral band of coloured photochromic films in different ormosil matrices

Fig. 3 Thermal bleaching kinetics (at dark) of the photochromic naphthopyran molecules in R-modified matrices

kinetics was observed in all samples. Both, the nature and amount of the organic substituents in the matrix play an important role in determining the kinetics of the thermal bleaching as they affect the polarity of the pore cage [25]. A faster bleaching is observed as the polarity of inner pore surface of the matrix is reduced. In this way, matrices with higher loadings of organic functional groups or matrices with less polar R groups show larger bleaching kinetic constants. The polar OH groups on the surface of the pores stabilize the coloured merocyanine (open form) resulting in a slower bleaching process. An interesting observation is that pPh-modified matrices show faster kinetics as compares with less polar matrices, such as Bu and Ph-modified matrices with the same relative amount of functional groups. This issue can be attributed to the strong interactions between the pPh groups and the OH groups on the surface of the pores (hydrogen bonds), which lead to a drastic reduction of the size

of the pores, increasing therefore the steric hindrance during the opening-closing mechanism. This effect can also be observed in the thickness of the resulting films, showing a much thinner film in pPh-modified samples ($0.75 \mu\text{m}$) as compared to samples modified with Ph groups ($1.2 \mu\text{m}$).

Photostability

The photodegradation of the photochromic naphthopyran dye upon prolonged exposition to UV light was measured in different ormosil matrices. The absorbance of the photochromic film was monitored vs. time while irradiating with a UV lamp, to follow the photodegradation of the photochromic molecules. It was found that the photodegradation of the naphthopyran dye is strongly affected by the composition of the embedding ormosil matrix. The introduction of organic substituents into matrices results in an important

Fig. 4 Photodegradation of a naphthopyran molecule embedded in Ph-modified matrices with different amount of Ph groups

reduction of the relative amount of silanol groups in the inner pore surface, where the molecules are allocated. This, in turn, has an important effect on the polarity of the matrix and therefore on the photostability of the dye molecules. The photodegradation of the naphthopyran molecules in the Sol-Gel matrices prepared here showed no yellowing of the matrix, even when exposed to UV-light for 120 h.

The photostability of the naphthopyran molecules in ormosil matrices is largely increased as the relative amount of the organic substituent is increased. Figure 4 shows the degradation curves of the dye in matrices with different loadings of Ph groups. Samples with R/Si ratios ≥ 0.3 show no difference in photostability since most of the NP molecules are in pores rich in Ph groups. The much faster photodegradation observed in matrices with R/Si ratios lower than 0.3 can be explained by the lower porosity of the matrices that

forces the NP molecules to occupy pores rich in OH groups. In this polar environment the zwitterionic forms of the open coloured form of the dye are stabilized, allowing the interaction with the pore surface via hydrogen bonding or ionic interactions [21], favouring the degradation of the photochromic molecules. The degradation of the naphthopyran molecules leads mainly to the formation of benzophenones, β -phenylcinnamaldehydes and other minor photoproducts [34, 38, 39].

An interesting behaviour was observed in the photostability of the photochromic films prepared with the same amount of different organic functional groups. The usage of larger organic functional groups in the ormosil resulted in a substantial increase of the photostability of the NP molecules in these matrices. Figure 5 shows the photodegradation of the photochromic dye in ormosil matrices prepared with

Fig. 5 Photodegradation of a naphthopyran molecule embedded in different ormosil matrices

different organic groups. In this way the photodegradation of the photochromic molecules in Ph-modified samples is reduced by a factor of 5, as compared with the photodegradation of the molecules in Et-modified matrices. The degradation of 30% of the photochromic molecules in Ph-modified matrices requires 116 h of irradiation, whereas it takes only 20 h in Et-modified matrices (Fig. 5). The decrease of the polarity of the pore environment, as larger organic groups are used in the ormosil, results in an increase of the photostability of the naphthopyran molecules.

Conclusions

The photostability of photochromic naphthopyran molecules embedded in different sol-gel prepared thin ormosil films depends strongly on the nature of the embedding matrix. The introduction of organic functional groups into the inner pore surface of the matrix allows tailoring the chemical environment where the dye molecules will be allocated. In this way, the spectral and dynamic properties, as well as the photostability of the photochromic dye in ormosil matrices can be controlled by the composition of the matrix in which the photochromic molecules are embedded. The photostability of the NP molecules shows a progressive increase as the polarity of the embedding matrix is reduced. At the same time a blue shift is observed in the absorption maxima of the coloured NP molecules while the thermal bleaching kinetics are substantially accelerated.

The ability to control the interactions between the photochromic molecules and the embedding ormosil matrix is very attractive from the point of view of future applications as it allows tailoring important properties of the photochromic materials.

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